

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF WET AND DRY SEASONS IN AKURE
BETWEEN 1971 AND 2020; IMPLICATIONS FOR AGRICULTURE, WATER
RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND HEALTH

BY

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ABSTRACT

One climatic variable of utmost importance in the determination of spatial and temporal patterns of climate variability in any given region is rainfall. It also provides useful information for water resource planning and increased agricultural production, (Abeysingha, et. al., 2014; Jain and Kumar, 2012; Khayse, et. al., 2016; Banerjee, et. al., 2010, Patra, et. al., 2012). Rainfall also plays a part in industrial and domestic water supply and in power generation. One important worldwide issue talked about mostly by scientists and researchers is climate change and one of its consequences is the change in rainfall patterns, (Khayse, et. al., 2015). Climate change has caused a lot of disasters such as wildfires, flooding, droughts, heat waves, etc around the world. This study was carried out to analyze comparatively the wet and dry season in Akure metropolis, a city in South-West geo-political zone in Nigeria. The time series rainfall and relative humidity data between 1971 and 2020 (50 years) obtained from Historical Weather API was used. The results show that wet season, WS rainfall Kendall's tau = +0.21; p-value = 0.012; z-score = +251, and s-score = 318. This implies a significant increase. The Dry season, DS rainfall Kendall's tau = -0.08; p-value = 0.342; z-score = -0.95 and s-score = -42. There was no significant trend. Humidity in the WS had Kendall's tau = -0.15; p-value = 0.078; z-score = -1.76, and s-score = -190. This is a marginal decrease and in the DS humidity, Kendall's tau = -0.22; p-value = 0.009; z-score = -2.61 and s-score = -278. This represents a significant decrease and it suggests that climate change and variability impact the wet season markedly in Akure.

Keywords: Climatic variable, climate change, rainfall, relative humidity, wet season, dry season

INTRODUCTION

Rainfall is the amount of precipitation in the form of liquid water droplets falling from the clouds to the Earth's surface. It is an important component of the water cycle as well as a key component of freshwater for drinking, for agriculture and the environment. Too much or too little rainfall can lead to floods or droughts respectively. Relative humidity is the amount of moisture present in the air compared to what the air can hold at that temperature, (Asin, 2025).

Climate change impacts the variability of hydro meteorological variables including rainfall, temperature, and evaporation, (Zhang, et. al., (2005), Scalzitti, et. al., (2016), Wang, et. al. (2017) and rainfall is the most important component of water cycle whose variability is closely related to drought and flood.

Nigeria is a West African country which experiences rainfall as a major form of precipitation. The rainfall so experienced varies in time and space. It also varies in the nature, duration, amount, distribution and intensity of occurrence. Gitau and Ogallo (2008) reported that, across Nigeria, rainfall is the most important climate variable showing highest disparity in both space and time and the disparity observed is either in intensity or distribution or both. Chup (2005) in his study reported that rain is a type of precipitation which connotes water droplets having a radius of between 0.5 to 7 mm and are mostly associated with convective clouds. A study by Audu *et al.* (2020) indicated that rainfall occur in peaks and cycles across Nigeria and a study by Syed *et al.* (2004) cited in Harris *et al.* (2007) reported that about 70%-80% of the noted disparity in terrestrial water cycle is attributed to rainfall. Abubakar (2015) corroborated the study and added that rainfall displays an important role in water cycle. Hence, rainfall is essential for functional and sustainable water cycle.

Several studies have shown that temporally and spatially, rainfall is the most variable climatic element in Nigeria whose variation can have significant impacts on economic activities, (Kowal and Kanabe, 1972; Kowal and Kassam, 1978; Adefolalu, 1986; Ayoade, 1993; Tsoho, 2008; Williams, Lizzi, 2008).

Rainfall is a major source of water including both surface and underground water and the hydrological cycle is enhanced by evaporation from water sources and wet surfaces, (Abubakar, 2015).

A number of hazards have been caused by excessive rainfall in Nigeria and several cases of huge landslides, flooding, massive water erosion and severe water pollution has been reported. Lawal *et al.* (2022) opined that, if there is a continuation of past trends of rising average global temperature; the type and frequency or intensity of precipitation storm characteristics will change, leading to the occurrence of extreme events including severe drought, intense water shortages as well as flooding. Rainfall variability is a major feature of climate change that could affect the hydrologic characteristics of a particular area because there can be an impairment of water availability leading to adverse effects on the environment, (UNFCCC, 2007). Ukhurebor *et al.*, (2017a, b, c, d) opined that climatic studies are more relevant due to its impacts in virtually all aspects of human existence. Several researches, for instance Ogundebi (2004) and Ologunorisa (2004) stated that intense rainfall may be the main cause of flooding and the increase in flooding due to the perceived increase in rainfall increases within the Southern part of Nigeria and poses enormous risk to lives and properties.

A study by Ayansina *et al.*, (2009) reported that variation in seasonal and annual rainfall is increasing in some parts of Nigeria. Variation in rainfall, being one of the major features of climate change and variability affect hydrologic characteristics of a particular area. This is because water availability can be impaired, leading to devastating effects on the environment, (UNFCCC, 2007). Ukhurebor and Abiodun (2018) in their study on variation in annual rainfall data of forty years (1978-2017) for South-South Nigeria reported that the area has an upward trend in rainfall between 1987 and 2017 and that this signifies more rainfall within the region which will definitely have effects on hydrologic characteristics of the area and possibly affecting the entire environment as it is noticed already.

As an element of climate change and variability, seasonal and annual rainfall variability in some parts of Nigeria is on the increase, (Ayansina *et al.*, (2009). The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) has predicted that the impacts of climate change and variability including

rising sea-level, droughts, heat waves, precipitation changes and flooding could push about 600 million people into food shortages by 2080 and about 1.8 billion people could face water scarcities, (UNDP, 2008).

Due to the impacts of climatic change in nearly every aspect of human existence, its studies have become more relevant recently (Ukhurebor et al., 2017a, b, c, d). Several researchers such as Ogundebi (2004) and Ologunorisa (2004) reported that flooding can be attributed to intense rainfall. Falaiye, et. al., (2021), in their study reported that there is variation in rainfall and presence of seasonality in the maximum and minimum amount of rainfall in a year at Enugu between 1980 and 2010. They added that on the analysis of a total of 372 months, only 88 months experienced minimal rainfall including November, December, January, and February and concluded that a serious dip was recorded in 1983 and this was followed by series of variation.

There have been various studies by a number of researchers on rainfall characteristics in Nigeria, some of which includes Olaniran (1990, 1992) as well as Olaniran and Summer, (1989), etc. They reported that there is a progressive early retreat of rainfall across the country, and consistently reported of a significant decline of rainfall frequency in September and October coinciding respectively with the end of the rainy season in northern and central parts of the country. Adejuwon (2010) reported that in South-Western Nigeria, there is occurrence of little dry season in the midst of wet season while Onyejekwe *et al.* (2016) added that there have been anomalies in the incidence and distribution of rainfall in the last two decades and that it has led to very erratic onset, cessation, duration and distribution of rainfall.

Akinbode , *et al.* (2006) in their study stated that Akure, the Ondo State Capital is located on longitude 5°18' E and latitude 7°17' N and it experiences a humid tropical climate with average annual rainfall of about 1500 mm. Average temperatures range from 26.2 °C to 30.4 °C, while its mean annual relative humidity ranges between 27.5 % and 98.2 %. Its vegetation is the tropical rainforest type. The impact of relative humidity on rainfall is of great importance because it contributes to the precipitation water in the atmosphere. The volume of relative humidity in the atmosphere contributes to the occurrence of rainfall over an area. From Yahaya *et. al.*, (2016) an upward trend in relative humidity above 0.6 mm indicates wetness and this implies that there exists a strong positive correlation between relative humidity and rainfall.

Oyewole, *et. l.*, (2014) further reported that a long rainy season begins in March, lasting till the end of July with a peak in June or July for Lagos, Port-Harcourt and Calabar. They observed that the period is characterized by thick clouds and is excessively wet particularly in the Niger Delta and coastal lowlands and is marked by high relative humidity with averages above 82 per cent in these stations. They averred that the stations experience a short dry season commonly referred to as “August Spell” in August and is followed by a wet period from early September through middle of October with a peak period towards September ending where the rains are not usually as heavy as those in the long rainy season. They opined that there is a strong relationship between relative humidity and rainfall - implying that an increase in relative humidity produces a corresponding increase in the possibility of cloudiness and subsequently precipitation. Thus, higher values of relative humidity are recorded during rainy seasons

A relative humidity value about, 80% and above is believed to creates a feeling of discomfort to humans due to a characteristic deliquescence of the salt on the surface of the skin (Tanabe & Kimura, 1994), and at 100% humidity, muggy conditions set in, (Shrestha *et. al.*, 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Study Area - Akure

Akure is the capital of Ondo State and a city in the South-West geo-political zone of Nigeria. It lies between latitude 7° 05' 0'' North of the Equator and longitude 5° 11' 42'' East of Greenwich Meridian. It has a total area of 991 square kilometer and an elevation of 351 m above sea level. Its population according to the 2006 population census was 403,000, (Macrotrends, (2022) and currently is estimated at 774,000, (Millenium city, 2010). Akure has a population density is 490/km², (Macrotrends, (2022). Akure is bounded by Ifedora to the North; Owo to the East and Idanre to the South and West. The town is situated in the tropical rainforest zone in Nigeria.

Akure is climatically in the tropical humid zone with two marked seasons; the wet and dry seasons, (NBS, 2009). It has an average annual temperature of 25.8 °C with a daily maximum temperature over 30 °C which is typical during the hot season and lasts about two months from late January to late March. March is the month with the highest average temperature of 30.5 °C and a nightly average of 22 °C. The cool season in Akure lasts for about 3.8 months running from mid-June to early October with a daily maximum temperature below 27.8 °C with August as the coolest month with average low and high of 20.5 °C and 26.6 °C respectively, (Weatherspark, 2024).

The average relative humidity in Akure ranges between 37 % and 88 %. During the dry season, (i.e. November to March), it is approximately low (lowest occurring between January and February) and varies between 37 % and 65 %. This period comes with reduced rainfall and accompanied with increasing temperatures (Asin, 2025). On the other hand, from April to October, the wet season sets in and relative humidity witnesses a significant rise with average between 62 % and 88 % with the peak occurring between August and September which are periods of heavy rainfall, (Weatherbase, 2025). The city has a total annual rainfall of 2,548 mm (Climate data, 2015) and September is the wettest month, with an average rainfall of 228.6 mm.

For about 2.4 months in Akure – between ending of November and early February, there is little or no rain with an average of about 5.1 mm with January being the driest month, (Weatherspark, 2024; OSACA, 2015).

was also tested to find out whether a relationship exists between the variables or not. The coefficient of variation (CV) was also employed to measure the degree of variability of the data.

- **Mann-Kendall (Mk) Test**

The Mann-Kendall test is non-parametric and is used widely in the detection of monotonic trends. It is superior to parametric tests (Karaburun *et al*, 2011; Ustaoglu, 2012; Karabulut, 2008) because it allows for missing values in time series data and does not require conformity to any particular distribution. It is robust to the effect of outliers (single data errors), (Turkes, 1999). The MK test is applied in testing for a decreasing or increasing trend in long-term temporal data, (Mallick *et. al.*, 2021). A p-value gives the probability of observing the trend by chance and a p-value <0.05 indicates or shows a statistical significance.

The Mann-Kendall equation is expressed as, (Kendall, 1975):

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sign}(X_j - X_i) \quad (1)$$

where n = number of data points, X_j and X_i = annual values in years j and i; $j > i$

The sign ($X_j - X_i$) is calculated from:

$$\text{sign}(X_j - X_i) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{for } (X_j - X_i) < 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } (X_j - X_i) = 0 \\ +1 & \text{for } (X_j - X_i) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The sign ($X_j - X_i$) simply implies the individual sign capability which takes on the values of +1, 0, or -1. A positive S value shows an upward or increasing trend, while a negative value indicates a downward or decreasing trend. A value of zero (0) indicates no trend.

The variance of the data is calculated in order to establish the probability of the Z value. That is, when n is greater than 8, statistic S approximates to normal distribution and the mean of S is 0 while the variance of S can be is computed as:

$$\text{Variance (Var (S))} = \frac{(n(n-1))(2n+5)}{18} \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of data points.

The values of S and Variance, Var (S) are used to compute the test statistics, Z which is obtained from the equation below:

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{V(S)}}; & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0; & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{V(S)}}; & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where S is the sign or the sum of the signs of all possible differences between later and earlier data points.

A value of $Z > 0$ indicates an increasing trend, while a value of $Z < 0$ gives a decreasing trend. In this study, a confidence level of 0.05 or 95 % was used. If the p-value is below 0.05, the trend is statistically significant.

Kendall's tau, τ (test statistics) is obtained from the equation below:

$$\tau = \frac{S}{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \quad (5)$$

where n = number of data points and S is the sign. The tau shows the strength and direction of the trend. It has a range of -1 to +1 which is analogous to the correlation coefficient in regression analysis. When both S and tau are positive, the trend is positive and when they are negative, a decreasing trend is indicated, Asin, et. al., (2025).

- **Sen's Slope Estimator**

The Sen's slope estimator was designed for checking the statistical linear relationships. It is used to calculate the magnitude of trends in a long-term temporal data, (Agarwal *et al.*, 2021), and is considered better to detect linear relationships because it is not affected by outliers in the data, (Ray *et al.*, 2021). Sen's slope estimator calculates the median of all possible pairwise slopes in the time series and the result gives the typical change in the parameter per year or per time units.

It is applied in this study to calculate the magnitude of the rate of change in the meteorological parameters under study and is expressed as:

$$Q_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{Y_j - Y_i}{j - i} & n = \text{odd} \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{\frac{N}{2}} + \left(Q_{\frac{N+2}{2}} \right) \right) & n = \text{even} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

A positive Q_{ij} value indicates an increasing trend, whereas a negative shows a negative trend in the temporal data. The unit of Sen's slope (Q_i) is the slope magnitude per year.

Given any N values of Y_j in time series, estimate of the slope is given as:

$$N = \frac{n(n-2)}{2} \quad (7)$$

where n is the number of data points.

- **Linear Regression Analysis**

Linear regression analysis is among the parametric models used in detecting a pattern in data series achieved and is done by fitting a linear equation to data observed. It establishes a relationship between two variables, the dependent and independent variables. The linear regression is done mostly with the scatter plot and is mathematically expressed as:

$$Y = mX + C \quad (8)$$

where Y = dependent variable (parameter values) and X, = independent variable (time in years), m = slope and C = intercept (constant coefficient).

The sign of the slope defines the trend variable direction – a positive value for an increasing trend and a negative value for a decreasing trend.

The regression analysis was used to establish a linear regression regarding time between the observed data results, (Aswad, *et. al.*, 2020).

- **Coefficient of Variation**

The coefficient of variation (CV) measures variability and indicates the size of a standard deviation in relation to its mean. It is a standardized, unit-less measure which makes for the comparison of variability between disparate groups and characteristics. It is expressed as (Statistics by Jim, 2019):

$$Cv = \frac{\delta}{\mu} \tag{9}$$

where δ = standard deviation and μ = mean.

A CV value below 10 % indicates low variability; above 90 % shows high variability and that ≤ 40 % shows stable climate, otherwise unstable.

RESULTS

Figure 2: Rainfall in Akure

Figure 2 above shows the rainfall pattern in Akure between 1971 and 2020 with linear regression equation,

$y = 0.98x - 345.28$ and R-squared (R^2) = 0.0088. Here, the rainfall is increasing as shown by Sen's slope in red.

Figure 3: Relative humidity in Akure

Figure 3 shows the relative humidity in Akure between 1971 and 2020 with linear regression equation, $y = -0.02x + 126.07$ and $R^2 = 0.0766$. The relative humidity is decreasing as indicated by Sen's slope in red.

Figure 4: Rainfall and Relative humidity in Akure

Figure 4 shows the relationship between rainfall and relative humidity throughout the study period (1971 – 2020).

Figure 5: Monthly variation of rainfall and relative humidity in Akure between 1971 and 2020

Figure 5 is a display of the monthly variation between rainfall and relative humidity throughout the period of study

SEASONAL DEFINITION

The wet season (WS) is defined as occurring between April and October, (7 months) while the dry season (DS) occurs between November and March, (5 months).

Highest WS rainfall was observed in 1973 (~1600 mm), indicating a particularly intense monsoon year whereas 1974 had the lowest rainfall in both seasons, hinting at potential drought conditions that year.

Highest DS rainfall was observed in 2017 (395.4 mm in July), indicating a particularly intense monsoon year whereas driest dry season occurred in 2005 (0 mm in January). The year, 1971 had the highest relative humidity of 94% and this was in September while the lowest humidity value of 31% was observed in December, 2015. On the other hand, 1974 had the lowest rainfall in both seasons, hinting at potential drought conditions that year.

Table 1: Mann-Kendall Trend Test Results

Parameter	Season	Tau	p-value	Z-Score	S-Stat	Trend Conclusion
Rainfall	Wet	0.21	0.012	+2.51	318	Significant increase
Rainfall	Dry	-0.08	0.342	-0.95	-42	No significant trend
Humidity	Wet	-0.15	0.078	-1.76	-190	Marginal decrease
Humidity	Dry	-0.22	0.009	-2.61	-278	Significant decrease

Table 1 shows the result of the Man-Kendall test. From here, rainfall in the wet season, (WS) has tau = 0.21, p-value = 0.012, Z-score = +2.51 and S = 318. Conclusively, the increasing (Z = +2.51) trend is significant (p = 0.02) at the 95 % confidence level (p<0.05). This is a statistically increasing trend.

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In the dry season, (DS) rainfall has $\tau = -0.08$, p -value = 0.342, Z -score = -0.95, and $S = -42$. The decreasing trend is not significant, ($Z = -0.95$; $p > 0.05$).

For relative humidity in the WS, $\tau = -0.15$, p -value = 0.078, Z -score = -1.76 and $S = -190$. This indicates a marginal decreasing trend which is significant, ($p = 0.078$). In the DS, $\tau = -0.22$, p -value = 0.009, Z -score = -2.61 and $S = -278$. This shows a significant decreasing trend for rainfall in the dry season.

Hence, rainfall increased significantly in the WS ($Z = +2.51$) and there was no change in the DS. Relative humidity on the other hand decreased significantly ($z = -2.61$), indicating drying in the DS and marginal WS decrease.

Table 2: Sen's Slope Estimator

Parameter	Season	Slope (unit/yr)	95% CI	Trend Magnitude
Rainfall	Wet	+1.84 mm/yr	+0.35, +3.33	Significant increase
Rainfall	Dry	-0.12 mm/yr	-0.45, +0.21	Marginal decrease
Humidity	Wet	-0.09 %/yr	-0.19, +0.01	Slight drying
Humidity	Dry	-0.17 %/yr	-0.29, -0.05	Significant drying ~8.5% drop (50 yrs)

Table 2 gives the result of the Sen's slope estimator. Here, rainfall in the WS increased at +1.84 mm per year at the 95 % confidence level which approximates to 92 mm increase over the five decades.

In the DS, rainfall decreased at -0.12 mm/year; a marginal decrease, though not significant ($p = 0.345$ in Table 1).

Relative humidity in the WS and DS decreased at -0.09 % and -0.17 % per year respectively indicating a slight significant drying and approximates to 8.5 % drop in the five decades.

Table 3: Variability Analysis

Parameter	Season	Mean	Std. Dev. (SD)	CV (%)	Variability Class
Rainfall	Wet	189.2 mm	45.3 mm	23.9	High
Rainfall	Dry	32.1 mm	28.7 mm	89.4	Extreme
Humidity	Wet	83.4 %	3.2 %	3.8	Very Low
Humidity	Dry	65.2 %	7.5 %	11.5	Moderate

Table 3 is the analysis of the variability in rainfall and relative humidity in both WS and DS.

It shows that rainfall in WS has a mean of 189.2 mm, SD of 45.3 % and a CV of 23.9 % as compared to the DS mean of 32.1 mm, SD of 28.7 % and a CV of 89.4 %.

Also from Table 3, relative humidity in WS has a mean of 83.4 %, SD of 3.2 and a CV of 3.8 %. In the DS, mean = 65.2 %, SD = 7.5 % and CV = 11.5 %.

Table 4: Comparative Summary of Wet and Dry Seasons

Metric	Wet Season	Dry Season
Trend (MK)	Rainfall increases, Humidity decreases	Rainfall stable, Humidity decreases
Sen's Slope, (SS)	+1.84 mm/year	-0.17 %/year
Variability (CV)	Moderate (23.9 %)	Extreme (89.4 %)
Standard Deviation, (SD)	45.3 mm	28.7 mm

Table 4 is a comparative summary of WS and DS rainfall and relative humidity in Akure between 1971 and 2020.

It showed that from the MK trend results, rainfall in WS is increasing significantly whereas relative humidity is decreasing. In the DS, rainfall is stable while humidity is decreasing.

From the SS estimator, the positive Sen's slope for wet season confirms the upward trend magnitude (1.84 mm/year) in rainfall in WS while in the DS, relative humidity decreases at 0.17 %/year.

Furthermore, the CV gives the level of variability in both seasons. Rainfall in WS varied moderately at 23.9 % while relative humidity varied extremely at 89.4 % in the DS.

DISCUSSIONS

The above results show wet season dominance. Averagely, about 82% of the total annual rainfall occurs during the wet season. The dry season shows lower rainfall totals with smaller fluctuations.

Rainfall in the dry season is highly erratic (CV = 89.4%) as compared to that in the wet season with a CV = 23.9%. This is corroborated by Adejuwon (2010) who reported that in South-Western Nigeria, there is occurrence of little dry season in the midst of wet season and Onyejekwe *et al.* (2016) also stated that there have been anomalies in the incidence and distribution of rainfall in the last two decades and that it has led to very erratic onset, cessation, duration and distribution of rainfall. Wang, *et al.* (2017) stated that rainfall experienced in Nigeria varies in time and space as well as in the nature, duration, amount, distribution and intensity of occurrence

Relative humidity on the other hand is more stable in the wet seasons, (CV = 3.8%) but variable in dry seasons, (CV = 11.5%). This agrees with Asin, (2025), who reported that average relative humidity in Akure ranges between 37 % and 88 % and during the dry season, (i.e. November to March), it is approximately low (lowest occurring between January and February) and varies between 37 % and 65 %. He added that this period comes with reduced rainfall and is accompanied with increasing temperatures. Thus, higher values of relative humidity are recorded during rainy seasons.

The standard deviation indicates greater variability in the wet season totals compared to the dry season. This is in consonance with Gitau and Ogallo (2008) who reported that rainfall is the most important climate variable over Nigeria showing highest disparity in both space and time and the disparity observed is either in intensity or distribution or both.

Wet seasons are getting wetter and show a statistically significant increasing trend, meaning rainfall during wet months has generally increased over time while dry seasons are becoming drier and less humid and shows a slight negative trend that is not statistically significant. Hence, dry season values are relatively stable over time. Ayansina *et al.*, (2009), in their study reported that seasonal

and annual rainfall variability which is an element of climate change and variability is on the increase in some parts of Nigeria.

Whereas the wet season was increasing and approximates to 92 mm increase over the five decades, the dry season decreased significantly showing significant drying and approximates to 8.5 % drop in the five decades. The results show that wet seasons are getting wetter, while dry seasons are becoming drier and less humid. At the monthly level, significant autocorrelation exists between consecutive wet season months ($r = 0.41$), while dry season months show weaker autocorrelation ($r = 0.17$). This stronger wet season autocorrelation suggests that persistence effects are more important during the wet season, potentially amplifying the impacts of the detected increasing trend.

IMPLICATIONS

Being that the wet seasons are getting wetter and the dry season, drier and as indicated by Tanabe & Kimura, (1994) that a high relative humidity of about 80% and above comes with a feeling of discomfort to humans a characteristic deliquescence of salt on the skin surface and Shrestha *et. al.*, (2019) added that at 100%, muggy conditions set in. This comes with implications for humans and the environment as follows:

- **Agriculture**

Crops benefit more during longer wet seasons as there is adequate moisture during wet months. Diverse crops are also supported. However, erratic dry seasons affect crop plants water intake. Hence, there may be need for irrigation to cushion the effect of water loss during the dry season. Longer wet seasons also favour multiple cropping seasons in wet years. On the other hand, heavy rainfall events may cause soil erosion, reducing land productivity.

- **Water Resources**

Increased wet-season rainfall enhances surface and groundwater recharge and also brings about flooding. There is potential for hydroelectric power generation during peak rainfall months.

- **Drought**

The variability and occasional low rainfall years pose drought risks and water scarcity during dry months impact agriculture and domestic water supply or use

- **Health**

Drier dry seasons may reduce malaria but increase dust-related respiratory issues which may be fatal for asthma patients, etc

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that there is strong seasonality with a pronounced wet season and significant inter-annual variability. The wet season in Akure generally indicates higher rainfall totals with somewhat lower relative variability (from the CV) but higher absolute variability (from the STD

DEV), reflecting the concentration of rainfall in these months. The dry season has lower rainfall totals but higher relative variability, meaning rainfall is more inconsistent during these months.

The statistical methods employed in this analysis provided a robust framework for detecting and quantifying these changes, offering valuable insights for climate adaptation planning and sustainable water management in a changing climate. Trend analysis using the Man-Kendall test and Sen's slope typically revealed that the wet season (WS) rainfall totals is increasing over the 50-year period, while the dry season (DS) showed less clear or no significant trend.

Hence, wet seasons are getting wetter, while dry seasons are becoming drier and less humid. This suggests that climate change and variability impact the wet season more markedly in Akure.

From the foregoing; the following recommendations are therefore suggested;

- **Agriculture**

Drought-resistant crop varieties should be adopted for dry years; soil conservation techniques such as contour farming and mulching should be practiced, and irrigation efficiency should be improved to optimize water use

- **Water Management**

For effective water management; reservoirs and dams should be built and maintained to capture excess wet season rainfall; rainwater harvesting should be implemented to improve water availability during dry months, and early warning systems should be developed for floods and droughts.

- **Infrastructure**

Good drainage systems should be enhanced in flood-prone areas; flood-resilient infrastructure designed to withstand heavy rainfall events, and urban greening with afforestation should be practiced to combat dry-season humidity drops.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Contribution and Originality:

This study contributes to existing literature on analysis of wet and dry seasons in Akure in particular and Nigeria in general. It serves as an eye opener to individuals and the government, thus helping them practice and introduce measures that will help mitigate the effects of climate change and improve agriculture.

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